

WAYS TO IMPROVE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article describes the formation of the child as a healthy and developed person as a starting point of continuing education, preparing children for school, forming the child as a healthy, developed, independent person, revealing their abilities. methods of teaching, the task of cultivating a passion for learning, systematic education.

Keywords: preschool education, emotions, abilities, thinking, play, intuition, developed, independent personality, psyche, ways of revealing abilities, systematic education, interest

INTRODUCTION

Preschool education is the primary part of continuing education. It ensures that the child develops into a healthy and developed person, stimulates the desire to learn and prepares him for systematic learning. Preschool education for children aged 6-7 is provided in state and non-state preschool institutions and in the family. The purpose of pre-school education is to prepare children for school, to form a child as a healthy, developed, independent person, to reveal their abilities, to cultivate a passion for learning, systematic education. The protection of the life and health of children in the pre-school educational institution is carried out by the medical staff of the pre-school educational institution and the state, as well as by the medical staff of the health authorities attached to the pre-school educational institution. Procedures and rules for the organization of protection of life and health of children in preschool education, rules of transportation of children to and from preschool education, requirements for security in preschool education, preschool education Requirements for the organization of fire safety in the institution, the requirements for the safety of the territory are regulated by the "Regulations on the organization

of protection of life and health of children in preschool institutions." In the pre-school period, a child's mobility, cognition and speech develop vigorously.

In it comes contemplation. His thinking is initially called "object (figurative) thinking", according to which the child is able to think about what he perceives, as well as about the things around him. Thinking at this age is expressed in the child's attitude to objects. His point is constantly evolving with his thinking. At the age of three, he learns the words used in everyday life, simple grammatical forms of speech. It is during this period that the senses, the emotions that express the attitude towards others, begin to appear.

The emotional state of a preschooler is reflected in the activity and intensity. At this age, the child begins to play, and his games are mainly to imitate the actions of adults and older children. He is more interested in what he is playing (puppets, toys) than in the content of the game. During pre-school education, the child begins to participate in social interactions in the kindergarten and family environment. As a child spends more time with adults and peers, his speech and thinking will improve. He tells in great detail about the events he saw and heard.

Communication and interaction with others begin to have a positive effect on the development of the child's behavior. As a result, it contains spiritual and moral judgments. The child now distinguishes between "good" and "bad" based on the behavior of others and their attitudes towards others. At this age, children understand the meaning of the words "you are good (bad)". The main activity of preschool children is play. Through the game, he learns about the environment and the nature of events that take place in it. At this age, the child draws based on his strength and skills, designs (constructs) different things, as well as makes things from different materials, clay, plasticine. At the age of six or seven, a child develops an interest in learning. School life seems interesting to him, he looks forward to the first day of school.

Primary school lessons have a special place in the education system due to their nature, goals and objectives. After all, it is based on the basics of literacy and moral education. Therefore, it is impossible to imagine the teaching of other subjects

without reading. The student encounters the text correctly, quickly, comprehensibly, mastering the content for the first time in reading lessons. Reading lessons allow students to acquire learning skills and knowledge required by the State Education Standards (SES). It is in the teaching of reading that a person's aspirations, first of all, to understand himself, as well as the world, are stimulated. Artistic, moral, educational, scientific and popular works are intended to provide a comprehensive understanding of various topics such as adult and children's life, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship and peace of peoples.

If reading lessons are organized in the form of introducing students to syllables, words and phrases during literacy training and reading them, storytelling based on pictures, reading after mastering the technique of reading is defined. on the selected artistic, scientific and popular texts on themes. Implementation of the requirements for reading education in the curriculum of primary education DTS and "Mother tongue" Proper organization of classroom learning, stages of teaching, principles and methods, in the first place, largely depend on the appropriate use of advanced pedagogical technologies. It is known that reading in the classroom is based on artistic and popular science texts. Introducing students to the text begins with the preparation for reading.

The preparatory phase includes information about the writers, students' understanding of the events described in the play, feeling the pathos of the work, unfamiliar and ambiguous words, interpretation of more complex figurative expressions. If the work is about the seasons, a trip to nature will also help to ensure the success of the class. After the first acquaintance with the text, asking the following questions will increase the activity of students in the classroom:

1. Which episode in the story do you find interesting?
2. Which of the protagonists of the story do you approve of? Which of my points do you disagree with?
3. Have you met such people in your life?

Accordingly, the leading feature of reading lessons is aimed at ensuring the literacy of students, as well as the introduction into the magical world of fiction,

educating them in the spirit of high moral values on the basis of national ideology. It is not possible to meet the requirements of the program by introducing Because the educational idea at the bottom of the text is revealed only as a result of understanding it. In other words, the magic of any work can attract the reader's attention when the hidden meaning of the text is understood. This is achieved through the acquisition of literary-theoretical concepts, the formation of skills of literary analysis.

The fact that students answer the teacher's questions in their own words during the analysis of the work also helps to think logically about the events described in the text, to correctly assess the actions of the protagonists. The questions are asked in a consistent manner, with no ambiguity or irrationality, based on a clear purpose, which allows students to gain a deeper understanding of the essence of the text being read. Because any answer requires independence. It should be noted that students should be taught to ask questions. As K. D. Ushinsky noted, the correct question is only half the answer. When asking questions about the text, the student's attention to the aspects of the subject of the lesson allows to learn the causal connections between the events described in the play, to draw vital conclusions. Therefore, asking questions about the text directs the reader to read consciously and comprehensibly. Its peculiarity is determined by the fact that it focuses on the correct formation of worldviews on the basis of the ideology of national independence by introducing students to the magical world of fiction.

The topics chosen for the reading lessons are aimed at educating students in everyday life, strengthening independence and human relations. The themes of independence, homeland, spirituality and nature stand out. Their goal is to awaken a sense of identity, independence, homeland and nature. With the help of nature topics, students gain knowledge about changes in nature, the change of seasons, and the animal kingdom. They teach students to be observant, to love nature, to have the right attitude to it. It is expected that the materials in the textbooks will expand from class to class, both in terms of subject matter and content.

The National Program of Personnel Training emphasizes the creation of advanced pedagogical technologies of education, modern teaching materials as one of the main tasks of general secondary education. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies clearly defines the scope of activities of the teacher and the student. Learning activities that are important in human life are carried out in all subject classes. However, it develops a reading methodology for teaching reading instruction. Teaching methods are improved on the basis of the general development of young students, achievements in the field of psychology, special methods. The effectiveness of reading lessons largely depends on the correct choice of teaching methods.

The term "method" is derived from the Greek language and is a set of methods for achieving a specific goal, practical and theoretical assimilation of existence. Therefore, teaching methods, like science itself, are constantly evolving. For example, in the old days, reading was taught on the basis of dry memorization, but now it is based on explanatory reading. In the method of memorization, no attention is paid to the interpretation of the words in the text, to the explanation of the meaning, to the retelling of what is read, in general, to the conscious reading. They provide more correct pronunciation, reading, expressive reading. The successors of K.D. Ushinsky's work introduced innovations in the method of annotated reading. Corf and Vakhterev say that reading is a means of real knowledge for students, while Vodovozov and Bunakov argue that knowledge is given to students in the process of reading in connection with the analysis of the work of art and the educational nature of the work. Professor Askar Zunnunov, reflecting on the content and methods of teaching, notes that the focus on students' acquisition of knowledge, and then memorization, is called explanatory reading in the educational process.

CONCLUSION

This means that reading is a reading that leads to thinking, feeling, fully comprehending the work, mastering the content of what is read. Annotated reading

provides an understanding of the content of the work, the main idea of the work, the idea put forward by the author.

Annotated reading is successful only if the following principles are fully followed.

1. Organization of study in connection with life.
2. Based on students' life experiences and impressions to make reading conscious and effective.
3. Demonstration of reading, excursions to nature, historical places, observation of flora and fauna, acquaintance with pictures, tables, objects and carrying out of the text in the form of expressive reading of the student.

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